

ORGANIZING FOREIGN LANGUAGE ATMOSPHERE AND MANAGEMENT IN EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10809753>

Abstract. *The Article gives information about quantity of learning foreign language among pedagogies and its importance in education system. And theoretical knowledge about language phenomenon among teachers. Modern methodology in teaching English and utilizing appropriate foreign language technology while creating new condition of organizing foreign language atmosphere in higher institutions. Supporting all learners by identifying barriers in curriculum design, learning materials and lesson design, and replaces the traditional instructional methods of interventions, accommodations, and differentiations for pedagogies identified as needing plans.*

Keywords: *Foreign language atmosphere, modern methodology, technologies, higher education, materials, foreign curriculum design, national and traditional condition in organizing foreign language atmosphere*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada pedagog o'qituvchilar orasida chet tilini o'rganish hajmi va uning ta'lim tizimidagi ahamiyati haqida ma'lumot beriladi. O'qituvchilarning chet til nazariy bilimlari darajasi shuningdek, oliy o'quv yurtlarida chet tili muhitini tashkil etish uchun yangi shart-sharoit yaratish, ingliz tilini o'qitishning zamonaviy metodologiyasi va tegishli chet tili texnologiyasidan foydalanish, o'quv dasturlari, o'quv materiallari va dars dizaynidagi to'siqlarni aniqlash orqali va an'anaviy ta'lim dasturlarini isloh qilib barcha o'rganuvchilarni qo'llab-quvvatlash*

Аннотация. *В статье представлена информация об уровне владения иностранным языком педагогами и его значении в системе образования. Уровень теоретических знаний иностранного языка преподавателей, а также создание новых условий для организации иноязычной среды в высших учебных заведениях, использования современной методики преподавания английского языка и соответствующих иноязычных технологий, образовательных программ, учебных материалов. и поддержка всех учащихся путем выявления препятствий на пути разработки уроков и реформирования традиционных учебных программ*

The ability to communicate in a foreign language and its role in learning science is incomparable. Even before the years of independence, special attention was paid to the teaching of foreign language, according to the sources, Methodists first dealt with the issue of teaching foreign languages in schools and wrote books from the 50s. For the first time, the 5th-6th grade textbooks created for Russian schools in Uzbekistan in the 1950s were adapted to Uzbek schools and included in the teaching process. In 1961-62, English was taught on the basis of a new textbook in the 5th-8th grades in Uzbek schools. In 1968, for the first time in Uzbekistan, a school program was created and published in English, German, and French. Later, various textbooks and manuals were created, and the Institute of Pedagogical Research of Uzbekistan took the lead in doing large-scale work. Today, in the rapidly developing period, educational institutions are introducing various innovative technologies and multimedia tools to teach English speaking skills. Technological tools are seen as ways to create a modern foreign environment and help the learner

improve language skills such as speaking skill. The Internet, videos, and speech recognition programs, especially modern programs such as Hot Potatoes, ISpring, EasyQuiz, MyTest, ELSA Speak, and Speaking assistant, are reckoned as the best tools for teaching speaking skills and evaluating easily. In addition, today electronic books, educational programs are attracting more readers attention.

It is known that for professional personnel to be aware of the news in exploring sphere all over the world and to acquire modern knowledge, to occupy all fields such as education, science, medicine, IT based on modern requirements, knowing foreign language skills.

In order to teach competitive personnel who can speak foreign languages fluently, many amendments and updates have been made to legal documents. If we look at history, for the first time the decision of the Council of Ministers of the SSR "On improving the study of foreign languages" in 1961 shows that the knowledge of foreign languages is important for specialists in various fields of science, technology culture and textbooks are developed for first and second year students of pedagogical institutes.

The task of developing innovative educational programs based on modern communicative competence methods for teaching foreign languages and assessing the knowledge of young students and introducing them to all stages of the educational system is also becoming an important task on the agenda. It is important to encourage more scientific activities focused on new approaches to teaching foreign languages, focusing on the practical effectiveness of scientific work. There is no doubt that the development and introduction of a system of practical testing of the methods developed by researchers directly in educational institutions will bring effective results. Materials related to teaching foreign language which organized according to different fields, modern teaching methods and knowledge assessment in non-philological educational areas and specialties of higher educational institutions of our country. Nowadays there are requires to create an electronic software platform that makes learning easy and convenient. The main goal of all such issues is to create modern and innovative pedagogical technologies, educational and methodological support for teaching foreign language and foreign language atmosphere in our country. A foreign language atmosphere is aimed at students' free and creative thinking, and deep training in specific directions in foreign language especially in English, and also it is depending on the abilities of every learner, it will have a good effect. For this purpose, it is necessary to create new textbooks, introduce advanced educational standards and methods into the educational system. In these processes, teachers, professors, and all people in education should be active and become active to learn language.

Today, for the purpose of in-depth teaching of foreign language, various decisions and orders, including the concept of teaching foreign languages and the national personnel training program have been developed in our republic. By knowing one foreign language can assist recognizing the world science, a learner or staff can go abroad to study in their specialty, expand foreign relations by studying international methods and technologies, return to Uzbekistan for the future development of our republic, and bring the country to the ranks of developed countries. Today, the problem of various programs and textbooks is being reformed within the framework of continuous teaching of the English language in our country.

Foreign experiences in using information technologies in development of professional activities of education students in the world education program continued to increase. Global information processes, which are taking place during the development of digital information and communication technologies, create the need to modernize the educational process. Due to the

further expansion of the demand for language education, the use of which is calculated with the help of international communication, the development of the language environment causes research and problems by pedagogical staff. The experience of developed countries such as Germany, USA, France, Finland, Switzerland and Great Britain, the productivity of modern educational technologies in establishing professional competence of future pedagogies, pedagogical education is going up to a new level of quality. In science of the world, scientific research is being carried out on the form, method and production of effective learning of language in production on the basis of metacompetencies, ensuring the competence of students in educational programs for innovative productions, providing modernized didactic systems.

Rapidly changing socio-economic phenomena, in particular, understanding the theoretical foundations of teaching foreign languages in a foreign language environment in higher education institutions, learning a foreign language independently, taking into account the critical and analytical thinking qualities of learners. The mechanism of ensuring the optimal integration of traditional and online education in the entire educational system based on the cluster approach requires the improvement of the didactic-methodical model of professional competence formation from both pedagogies and students in the conditions of the digital educational environment.

According to Methodology of foreign language teaching, prof. Mikhail Vasilievich Lyakhovitsky, it is a science that studies the goals, content, means of education, as well as the methods of education using a foreign language. Basically, it teaches the following three major topics: theoretical problems of foreign language teaching, teaching speech activities and organizational issues of foreign language teaching.

It can be seen from the experience of the world and Uzbekistan that the form of distance education supplemented by online formats is spreading widely as an alternative form of education in the higher education system. In this way, the form of remote, webinar education is currently developing in our country. Due to the rapid development of Internet technologies, the student is no longer required to be in the classroom under the supervision of the teacher, but the student can complete the assigned tasks and acquire knowledge, skills and experience. Even a person who is in different parts of the world can get an online education without leaving his home, listening to audio and video lectures, completing the assignments and successfully completing the course and getting a certificate.

Based on foreign experiences, Wilson, Nancy, knowing that the materials, textbooks and programs used in creating a foreign language environment are of great importance, chooses the most appropriate resource as a result of organizing questions and answers from the learners.

Osman Hassan conducted research on the importance and methodology of using strategies in teaching, and according to him, the teacher uses the strategies and methods chosen by the students during the lesson, taking into account the interests and desires of the students, to help the students learn more and will be the motivation to search for them.

Professor Abosnan Salem Hamed of the University of Glasgow explained that creating a foreign language environment by using audio and video materials during the lesson, students can learn foreign languages quickly and effectively.

Viktor Ekblom, a teacher at the University of Malmö, in his article emphasizes that he can help students understand a foreign language through viewing, i.e. organizing a lesson with the help of various posters, videos and photos. In this case, the text and the corresponding pace or video are given with textbook during the lesson.

Baker Richard professor of Neumann University, chooses the teaching method based on stories in teaching a foreign language, according to which the students will have to read the given story, understand it and give it a speech. This method helps students develop both reading and speaking skills.

Today, not only in Uzbekistan, but throughout the world, English is recognized as the world language and is being taught and studied as a second language, however, there are still shortcomings and problems in its full mastery. As a way to overcome such problems, it is one of the important problems to improve the foreign language competence of students and teaching staff in higher education institutions, and to form knowledge and skills that meet foreign requirements. In order to ensure the speech, writing and grammar activities of teachers in foreign language, a number of measures are being taken in Uzbekistan, as well as in the rest of the world.

The role of the foreign language environment in quality control of the educational process is of great importance today, because the presence of a foreign language environment in higher education institutions shows that the teaching methods are new, that they can meet foreign requirements, and that pedagogies and students have modern competencies. Participation in supervision and production classes for various purposes in determining the foreign language environment, conducting contests with foreign language teachers on the comprehensive provision of educational programs for professions and subjects, organizing professional skill competitions in a foreign language, organizing methodical seminars, training courses.

To study in a modern foreign environment, it is necessary to have modern equipment, samples, equipment, technical means of teaching. A well-organized educational process allows the teacher to achieve a high quality of mastering the program materials. All participants of the educational process: both the administration, pedagogical staff, and the students themselves must understand this environment and foreign language education, and feel the level of importance. In education, motivation and interest in academic work, cognitive activity, subject matter is an important factor in the effectiveness of education. Motivation should be considered and presented in conjunction with other factors. Not only pedagogies, but students themselves are responsible for the quality of education, all other things being equal, there will always be relatively stronger or weaker receivers, and it is important to include passive learners as assets in the organization of lesson and they differ according to their age, gender and field of study. If education covers the entire structure of quality higher education institutions, then there is a chance to achieve educational efficiency.

The foreign language atmosphere in higher education opens the way for him to attract students and teaching staff, to improve the foreign language skills of pedagogues, and to improve the quality of education in higher education. The lack of knowledge of the language, which is common among all non-philology teaching staff, is the reason for relying on pedagogical programs. It includes foreign requests and any favorable conditions for pedagogues. So, we base it on the basis of experience in organizing the language environment on the basis of nationality.

In conclusion, I thought it appropriate to quote the following thoughts of the president of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev: "We must create all the conditions for the youth of our country, which gave the world such great scholars and saints as the Bukhariy, Beruniy, Termiziy, Moturidiy, and Khorezmiy, so that they can grow up worthy of their great ancestors." So, relying on the determination and courage of our great ancestors, the strong will of our people, and our mature generation that is growing up, it is the most urgent task of pedagogies to consistently continue the path of radically renewing the life of our society. In particular, "Salvation is in education, salvation

is in upbringing, salvation is in knowledge." Because all goals are achieved through knowledge and education." The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

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